

Nitritometric Determination of Pharmaceutical Primary Arylamines Using Aminoanthraquinone Dyes as Internal Indicators**

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A study has been made for the first time concerning the use of Sudan Blue GN, Sudan Green 4B, Alizarin Viridin, Alizarin Violet 3B or Alizarin Brilliant Violet R as an internal indicator in the nitritometric titration of aromatic primary amines such as sulphonamides (pure and in formulations), procaine, benzocaine and other compounds containing free arylamino group or yielding the same through hydrolysis or reduction. The end points are sharp and the results are accurate within $\pm 0.2\%$ on macro, $\pm 0.4\%$ on semimicro and $\pm 2.5\%$ on micro scale determinations. The titration procedures are simple and rapid.

RECENTLY we have reported the use of two aminoanthraquinone dyes, Oracet Blue B and Alizarin Brilliant Blue BS as internal indicators in the nitritometric determination of several aromatic primary amines¹. Apart from these, no other aminoanthraquinone dye seems to have been reported as indicator either in acid-base or nitritometric assay of primary arylamines. Our investigations have now shown that the five aminoanthraquinone dyes, Sudan Blue GN (SB GN), Sudan Green 4B (SG 4B), Alizarin Viridin (AV), Alizarin Violet 3B (AV 3B) and Alizarin Brilliant Violet R (ABV R), (Colour Index Numbers: 61520, 61565, 62560, 60725 and 60730 respectively) can also be used as internal indicators in the nitritometric determination of several sulphonamides, local anaesthetics (procaine and benzocaine) and other drugs (pure and in pharmaceutical preparations) containing the free arylamino group or yielding the same by hydrolysis (phthalylsulphacetamide and phthalylsulphathiazole) or reduction (chloramphenicol). We have observed that these dyes can be successfully employed as internal indicators at room temperature in the titrations of sulphonamides which produce coloured diazonium salts as well unlike as many as the 15 internal indicators reported so far by several workers²⁻⁹.

Experimental

Reagents :

All the sulphonamides, procaine, benzocaine and chloramphenicol were either I.P. or B.P. grade and their purity was checked by the B.P. methods¹⁰.

0.2% solutions of all the aminoanthraquinone dyes obtained from M/s. Chroma-Gesellschaft were

prepared in double distilled water excepting SB GN and SG 4B which were prepared with alcohol (0.2% solutions).

Sodium nitrite (BDH-AnalaR) solutions (0.05, 0.02 or 0.005 N) were prepared and standardised by the dead stop titration using the purified sulphuric acid¹⁰.

Always Basynt AR Hydrochloric acid was used.

Procedure for Compounds having Free Arylamino group :

An aliquot volume of the sample solution was treated with sufficient hydrochloric acid (1:1) so as to maintain an overall acidity of 3.0-6.0 M in hydrochloric acid. 0.20-0.30 ml of 0.2% indicator solution was added and titrated slowly with sodium nitrite solution (0.05, 0.02 or 0.005 N), introducing the titrant under the surface of the solution with a burette having an elongated tip. In the vicinity of the end point, the tip was withdrawn, one or two drops of indicator solution added and the titration was completed by adding the titrant dropwise until a sharp colour change is obtained. The colour change at the end point is pink to green with SB GN, golden yellow to green with SG 4B, green to greenish yellow with AV or pinkish blue to blue with AV 3B or ABV R.

No indicator correction was necessary for the titrations with 0.1 N or 0.05 N sodium nitrite solutions. However, indicator correction was necessary in the usage of still lower concentrations of sodium nitrite solutions as three drops of SB GN, SG 4B or AV and AV 3B or ABV R solutions consume 0.04

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ml and 0.20 ml of 0.005 *N* sodium nitrite solution respectively.

Procedure for Phthalylsulphacetamide and phthalylsulphathiazole :

The accurately weighed sample or the aliquot volume of the sample solution was boiled with 50 ml of dilute hydrochloric acid for 30 min under reflux condenser, cooled and completed the assay as mentioned above starting with the words "0.20 - 0.30 ml of indicator.....".

Procedure for Chloramphenicol :

About 0.25 g of chloramphenicol sample was accurately weighed, 10ml concentrated hydrochloric acid and in small portions 2.5 g of zinc dust were added and allowed to stand for one hour. Later it was filtered through cotton wool and washed the residue with water. The combined filtrate and washings were diluted to 50 ml and completed the assay as mentioned before.

Representative results from a large number of titrations in the determinations of sulphonamides, procaine, benzocaine and chloramphenicol in pure samples and pharmaceutical preparations were presented in Tables 1 and 2 using SB GN and AV as typical indicators.

Results and Discussion

The purity values obtained in the analysis of various sulphonamides, procaine, benzocaine and chloramphenicol using these five indicators were in good agreement with those values obtained by the official B.P. titrimetric procedures¹⁰ (Table 2). As seen from the Tables 1 and 2, the methods were appeared to be simple with better than $\pm 0.1\%$, 0.4% and 2.5% accuracies on macro, semimicro and micro scales respectively. These aminoanthraquinone dyes

TABLE 2—ASSAY OF SULPHONAMIDES IN PHARMACEUTICAL PREPARATIONS*

Name of the dosage form and the active substance	B.P. method	% Labelled amount	
		Proposed method**	AV
		SB GN	
<i>Tablets :****</i>			
Sulphaguanidine I.P.	99.85	99.85	100.00
Sulphadimidine I.P.	99.65	100.70	100.20
Sulphadiazine I.P.	99.70	100.10	100.10
Sulphamethoxypyridazine B.P.	100.10	100.15	100.05
Sulphasomidine B.P.	99.70	99.90	99.90
Sulphapyridine B.P.	99.70	99.85	99.90
Sulphadimethoxine B.P.	99.50	99.75	99.60
Phthalylsulphathiazole I.P.***	98.60	98.85	98.90
<i>Injections and eye drops****</i>			
Sulphadiazine injection B.P.	100.60	100.60	100.60
Sulphacetamide sodium I.P.	99.65	98.75	98.80
eye drop:			

* Each result is an average of 5 separate analyses.

** Similar results obtained with SG 4B, AV 3B and AV R.

*** After carrying hydrolysis.

**** These were market products of different manufacturers.

were found to be advantageous over the remaining internal indicators so far developed for two reasons. Estimations of sulphonamides which produce coloured diazonium salts can be carried out successfully as the diazonium salt colour does not interfere with the indicator colour change at the end point. The assay of sulphonamides, procaine and benzocaine at microgram level can also be carried out with reasonable accuracy. SB GN, SG 4B and AV were appeared to be better among the five dyes used. As the diazotisation process in considerably faster with the compounds estimated (Tables 1 and 2), addition of potassium bromide, sodium bromide or sodium nitrate to the reaction mixture during the titration is not necessary.

Interferences : The determinations were not affected by using these dyes as indicators, in the presence of reductants such as sulphurous acid, formic acid, hydroquinone even if they are present

TABLE 1—ASSAY OF SULPHONAMIDES, PROCAINE BENZOCAINE AND CHLORAMPHENICOL.*

Name of the compound	Maximum % error**					
	Sudan Blue GN			Alizarin Violet		
	macro	semimicro	micro	macro	semimicro	micro
Sulphanilamide	0.08	0.20	1.4	0.10	0.30	1.8
Sulphacetamide	0.06	0.25	1.8	0.05	0.30	2.0
Sulphamethoxazole	0.20	0.30	1.6	0.08	0.35	2.2
Sulphamerazine	0.15	0.35	2.0	0.15	0.25	2.2
Sulphaphenazole	0.22	0.40	2.4	0.20	0.40	2.4
Procaine hydrochloride	0.15	0.25	1.8	0.18	0.25	1.6
Benzocaine	0.20	0.20	1.5	0.15	0.25	1.8
Phthalylsulphacetamide***	0.10	0.10	2.2	0.20	0.40	2.4
Chloramphenicol****	0.25	0.35	—	0.25	0.40	—

* Values obtained from at least six determinations.

** Similar results obtained with the other indicators, SG 4B, AV 3B and AV R.

*** After carrying hydrolysis.

**** After carrying reduction.

Amount taken for, Macro : 250 mg, semimicro : 25 mg, micro : 250 μ g.

in 10 fold molar excess with respect to the amine compound. Oxidising agents must be absent. Ca^{++} , Zn^{++} , ephedrine, codeine, sugar, lactose, starch, magnesium stearate, trimethoprim, adrenaline, alcohol or acetone usually present as adjuncts or binding materials in various pharmaceutical preparations of the amine compounds have no influence on the accuracy of the results.

The transition potentials (mv vs N.H.E.) for the sulphanilamide titration in 3.0 M hydrochloric acid medium are SB GN : 885 ± 10 , SG 4B : 905 ± 15 , AV : 900 ± 10 , AV 3B : 930 ± 15 and ABV R : 935 ± 15 .

We believe that, as all the five aminoanthraquinone dyes possess one or two secondary amino substituents, the colour change at the end point in the nitritometric assay may be due to the formation of N-nitroso compounds.

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